

TerraDrought - a global drought monitoring, forecasting and impact reporting system

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ABSTRACT: Current drought monitoring and impact data collection efforts are fragmented, often limited to retrospective analysis conducted separately and with delays that create disconnects and information gaps. Most existing systems also lack a forecasting component, and no publicly available tool currently integrates drought monitoring, forecasting, and impact analysis. To address this critical gap, we have developed TerraDrought - a globally relevant and accessible drought information portal. At its core, TerraDrought is designed to provide integrated, timely, and accessible drought information for a wide range of users worldwide.

SIGNIFICANCE STATEMENT: In an era of limited global drought datasets and constrained funding for global drought research, science investigations can benefit from quick and unhindered access to existing datasets to advance drought forecasting and timely impact mitigation activities. A new TerraDrought portal provides the community with a new centralized source for highlighting drought indicators, impacts and forecasts, which builds on decades of drought research from the principal collaborators.

1. Introduction

Drought is one of the most common and complex natural hazards affecting the environment, economies and populations globally (*Sheffield et al., 2012; Wilhite et al., 2016; Spinoni et al., 2021; Toreti et al., 2024*). Recent analyses of soil moisture trends (*Řehoř et al., 2024*) indicated prevailing drying trends on all continents. This is in line with growing atmospheric evaporative demand, which has increased significantly (*Gebrechorkos et al., 2025*) since 1901. Gebrechorkos et al. (2025) also indicated that during the past 5 years (2018–2022), the areas in drought have expanded by 74% on average compared with 1981–2017. At the same time, future development projections (e.g. *Trnka et al., 2019*) indicate that further increases in the drought-affected area and frequency are almost certain to grow.

The rise of national-scale online drought monitoring systems, as we understand them today, started in the mid-1990s. With hindsight, this development interestingly took place in times where a change in the drying trends can be identified in the time series analyses. What started, e.g. with the US Drought Monitor (e.g. *Svoboda et al., 2002*) or the Czech and Slovak Drought Monitor (*Trnka et al., 2020*) as country-oriented efforts continued to joint efforts covering larger regions or entire continents (e.g., North American Drought Monitor or European Drought Observatory, etc.). Operational reporting of drought impacts started later and has so far been mostly confined to individual countries or specific sectors (e.g., US Drought Impact Reporter (2005), Czech and Slovak national drought impact reporting networks (2012)), and only recently have we seen the first global impacts monitoring efforts (*Hlavsová et al., 2025*).

Therefore, studies linking meteorological anomalies to observed drought impacts must rely on observational (retrospective or prospective) data. This limits the ability to test direct cause-and-effect relationships between drought severity and its impacts and introduces potential selection bias, as external factors influencing both variables cannot be fully controlled. At the same time, while regional drought impact catalogues (e.g., the US Drought Impact Reporter (DIR) and the European Drought Impact Database (EDID)) are excellent tools, they lack global coverage and operational flexibility. Shared limitations of EDID and the DIR are that 1) these tools depend on human attention, such as accounts in news stories, which tends to focus on extreme events, leading to documentation of impacts but not the circumstances leading to impacts, and 2) there is not a widely agreed-upon methodology for utilizing narrative data in general-purpose monitoring systems, particularly for a multi-sector, slow-moving hazard such as drought. Simultaneously, few drought monitoring tools connect seamlessly to forecasts or outlooks. Despite significant progress in establishing drought monitoring systems, their availability remains highly uneven, with some regions still lacking the capacity to monitor or forecast drought conditions and impacts effectively.

To contribute to overcoming the deficiencies listed above, the TerraDrought initiative was launched in November 2025. Its goal is to meet the need for real-time drought monitoring and forecasts coupled with independent drought impact acquisition. This would allow for quicker and more objective evaluation of ongoing events and potential attribution studies and contribute to a more objective reporting of drought events, while providing decision-makers, journalists and the public with timely information in an accessible form. As the system provides publicly available data and its visualization in real time, it can also serve as a stopgap measure when regional or national systems are not yet in place.

2. TerraDrought make-up and features

2.1 TerraDrought architecture and available datasets

The TerraDrought architecture provides a unique combination of data archive, drought monitoring, and forecasting, complemented by global monitoring of drought impact reports. The platform's main components include the interactive map viewer, data highlights dashboard, and data archive browser (Figure 1).

Figure 1: TerraDrought map viewer landing page including interactive map viewer, dataset timeline, dataset area chart, description box, and basic user interface tools (available at <https://terradrought.eu/> and <http://terradrought.unl.edu/>)

The interactive map viewer provides quick access to the latest data and forecasts. It provides standard functions for visualizing and interacting with spatial data. In addition to the data view, it includes a timeline navigation through the past year of available data and forecasts for the datasets that include forecasting components (Table 1). The data highlights dashboard includes summary statistics and highlights from all the data and might be used as a quick navigation tool for the current global drought and drought impacts. The archive browser provides access to the whole history of the available data for all the included datasets.

Table 1: Pilot set of the TerraDrought available datasets

Dataset name	Dataset description	Available subsets	Technical note	Components	Input data
SoilClim drought intensity	Drought intensity compares the actual amount of water available to plants with the values recorded for the given area during the same time period of the year between 1961 and 2010. Each	0-10 cm, 0-40 cm, 0-100 cm, 40-100 cm	GeoTIFF, 10 km spatial resolution, EPSG: 4326, 1981-present, daily	Monitoring, Forecast	ERA-5 Land (C3S, 2025), SoilGrids (Hengel et al., 2017), ECMWF IFS

Dataset name	Dataset description	Available subsets	Technical note	Components	Input data
	drought intensity class represents a particular drought period return probability.				(ECMWF, 2025)
SoilClim soil moisture deficit	Available water deficit is the amount of water in mm/inch per the visualized soil column that is missing (or is in surplus) compared to the common levels (average of 1961 to 2010) of available water at the given site and time of the year. Negative values represent less water than usual while positive values represent a higher available water amount than is common.	0-10 cm, 0-40 cm, 0-100 cm, 40-100 cm	GeoTIFF, 10 km spatial resolution, EPSG: 4326, 1981-present, daily	Monitoring, Forecast	ERA-5 Land (C3S, 2025), SoilGrids (Hengel et al., 2017), ECMWF IFS (ECMWF, 2025)
SoilClim relative soil saturation	Readily available soil water represents the amount of water available to plants as a proportion of the maximum soil water content that can be permanently held within the given soil column. Units are % where 0% represents no water available to plants (i.e. wilting point) and 100% represents water content held in the soil after excess water has drained away (i.e. field capacity). In general	0-10 cm, 0-40 cm, 0-100 cm, 40-100 cm	GeoTIFF, 10 km spatial resolution, EPSG: 4326, 1981-present, daily	Monitoring, Forecast	ERA-5 Land (C3S, 2025), SoilGrids (Hengel et al., 2017), ECMWF IFS (ECMWF, 2025)

Dataset name	Dataset description	Available subsets	Technical note	Components	Input data
	most plant species cannot survive values close to 0%, at values below 30% visible signs of water stress will be apparent on most plant species and at values below 50% (i.e. stress point) plants start to be limited by soil water availability.				
Drought impacts	Drought impact reports collected from open-access text mining of global media online articles since 2022.	4 weeks, 12 weeks	GeoJSON, country level, EPSG: 4326, 2022-present, monthly, 3 monthly	Monitoring	Global online media scraping (<i>Hlavsová et al., 2025</i>)
Standardized Precipitation Index	Standardized Precipitation Index is a standardized measure of how much precipitation has fallen over a chosen time period compared to the long-term average (commonly 1961–2010). Values below zero indicate drier-than-usual conditions, while values above zero show wetter-than-usual conditions. The more extreme the value, the stronger the anomaly.	3 months, 6 months, 12 months, 24 months	GeoTIFF, 10 km spatial resolution, EPSG: 4326, 1981-present, monthly	Monitoring	ERA-5 Land (C3S, 2025)
Standardized Precipitation	Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index extends the SPI	3 months, 6 months,	GeoTIFF, 10 km spatial resolution, EPSG:	Monitoring	ERA-5 Land (C3S, 2025)

Dataset name	Dataset description	Available subsets	Technical note	Components	Input data
Evapotranspiration Index	approach by including not only precipitation but also the amount of water lost to the atmosphere through evaporation and plant transpiration. This makes it sensitive to both lack of rainfall and heat-driven drying. Negative values represent drier and hotter-than-usual conditions, while positive values indicate wetter or cooler conditions than normal.	12 months, 24 months	4326, 1981-present, monthly		
Palmer Drought Severity Index	Palmer Drought Severity Index combines precipitation, temperature, and soil moisture data to estimate long-term drought severity. It reflects the cumulative balance between water supply and demand in the soil over months to years. Negative values represent persistent drought, while positive values indicate prolonged wetness.		GeoTIFF, 10 km spatial resolution, EPSG: 4326, 1981-present, monthly	Monitoring	ERA-5 Land (C3S, 2025), SoilGrids (Hengel et al., 2017)
Z-score	The Z-score shows how much the current value of a variable (such as soil moisture) differs from its long-term average, expressed in standard deviations. A negative Z-score means		GeoTIFF, 10 km spatial resolution, EPSG: 4326, 1981-present, monthly	Monitoring	ERA-5 Land (C3S, 2025), SoilGrids (Hengel et al., 2017)

Dataset name	Dataset description	Available subsets	Technical note	Components	Input data
	conditions are drier than normal, and a positive score means wetter than normal. The larger the absolute value, the stronger the anomaly.				

2.2 Quick guide to the TerraDrought platform use

The TerraDrought portal provides users with an integrated view of global drought conditions, reported impacts, and forecasts. Coming to the TerraDrought portal landing page, users see thumbnail maps of drought intensity and reported drought impacts worldwide, with buttons to access more detailed maps. The data highlights dashboard for drought intensity shows the percentage of each continent in drought, including how much it has changed in the past seven days, the number of people in drought, and the seven-day forecast for the same metrics. Highlight panels for reported impacts show categories for reported impacts for the past 30 days, the countries most affected and how report counts have changed in the past 30 days.

On the Maps tab, TerraDrought users first see a global map of Drought Intensity based on soil moisture, with options to view calculations for four different depths. Scrolling horizontally allows users to choose other datasets and subsets to map, as listed in the table above. A data archive allows users to download the drought indicators that are part of the portal, with drought indicators back to the 1960s and impacts back to 2022. Metadata is under the About tab.

3. Showcasing recent drought events with TerraDrought capabilities

The Amazon (Fig. 1e, highlighted in blue) Basin has experienced an extreme drought that started in the austral summer of 2022-2023 and extended into 2024 (e.g., *Marengo et al., 2024*). The event coincided with an intense El Niño and abnormally warm tropical North Atlantic Ocean temperatures. As a result, the Negro River reached its lowest water level in 120 years (*Maciel et al., 2024*), and up to an 80% reduction of open water extent was reported. The drought event was recorded well by the below-normal Standardized Precipitation Evapotranspiration Index (SPEI3), showing over 40% of the area in drought conditions from June 2023 to the end of 2024 (Fig. 1a), with two peaks of drought event area in the fall months of 2023 and 2024. The soil moisture deficit (SMD) in the 0-100 cm soil profile depth (Fig. 1a) shows corresponding peaks in area in drought conditions (values below 20 mm water deficiency). The impact reports indicate a response to the media-reported drought impacts with two spikes in total report count (Fig. 1b), with more significant impacts occurring with the second consecutive drought spike in fall 2024. During the first examined event, the reported impacts describe negative consequences of drought in hydrology, waterborne transportation and ecosystem conditions,

compared to the second spike showing a higher share of impact reports describing increased wildfire risk activity and agricultural impacts.

The second example of the TerraDrought data use covers an area of North Africa/Middle East/Central Asia from Libya in the west to Afghanistan in the east and includes the Afro-Eurasian land bridge (Fig. 1e, highlighted in green). In contrast to the Amazon Basin, no single event affected the region. However, it allows for showing the potential benefit of the portal to assess the general drought status across borders, including countries where data are difficult to obtain. The area affected by drought conditions is more prominent when examining SPEI3, showing the peak drought area in the summer of 2025 (Fig. 1c). The SMD does not capture widespread drought conditions. Still, the impact record occurrence in time follows the drought signal from the SPEI3 (Fig. 1d), showing the accumulation of reported impact reports at the end of the examination period. The most prevalent impact categories include hydrology, societal impacts and agriculture.

Figure 2: Drought conditions between 2023 and 2025, shown as the share of area with soil moisture deficit (SMD, 0–100 cm) < -20 mm and 3-month SPEI < -1 for (a) the Amazon region and (c) the North Africa–East Mediterranean region. Panels (b) and (d) show the share of impact categories and the total number of drought impact reports by month for the same regions. Map (e) indicates countries included in the Amazon (green) and NAEM (blue) regions.

4. Future enhancements for the TerraDrought platform

The TerraDrought portal is designed as a seamless gateway that integrates drought monitoring, impacts, and forecasts to support decision makers, the media, and the public. A key feature of the portal is its adaptability. New indicators, including advanced composite measures, can be incorporated into its suite of outputs as they are developed. For instance, work is already underway on a hydrological and agricultural composite drought indicator, which will be added once available. Beyond monitoring, the portal will advance understanding of how drought indicators connect with real-world impacts. To this end, machine learning is increasingly used to analyze and recognize patterns across regions and seasons, while natural language processing (NLP) is extracting geographically specific drought impacts from diverse sources such as news media, social media, and unstructured datasets. The open platform format also provides an option to integrate or point towards already existing impact databases and provides a strong basis for impact-based forecasting methods. In addition, integrating global agricultural databases will enhance the portal's ability to link drought conditions with critical sectoral outcomes, ensuring a more comprehensive and actionable information resource that will continually evolve as more information and products become available.

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